

MODELING OF DAMAGE AND PERMEATION IN POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES AT CRYOGENIC TEMPERATURES

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Summary: Polymer matrix composite (PMC) materials are ideal for aerospace structural applications, such as cryogenic fuel tanks of Reusable Launch Vehicles (RLVs) and Expendable Launch Vehicles (ELVs), due to their high strength-to-weight and stiffness-to-weight ratio. For the confident application of these materials, it is necessary to evaluate the permeation of cryogenic fuel caused due to transverse matrix cracks in conjunction with inter-ply delaminations resulting in an intersecting network of passages. In this paper, an expression for predicting delaminated crack opening displacement (DCOD) is derived based on first-order shear laminate theory applied to five-layer and three-layer models. The DCOD obtained using the five-layer is verified using a two-dimensional finite element analysis. A mathematical model to predict permeability in graphite-epoxy laminate system (IM7/PETI-5) is developed using Darcy's law for isothermal, viscous flow of gases through porous media. The results obtained from both five-layer and three-layer model are used as input to the permeability model. Using this model, the permeability is calculated for an orthotropic laminate lay-up for a given delamination length, crack density and loading conditions. In addition to the $[0/90]_s$ cross-ply configuration, the model is enhanced to include laminates with arbitrary ply orientations. Model predictions of DCOD are compared with 3-D FEA results for a $[45/0/-45/90]_s$ laminate for verification.

Keywords: Shear deformable plate theory, permeation, cryogenic fuel, delamination, transverse matrix cracks.

I. Introduction

Structural weight reduction through the use of advanced materials and manufacturing is one of the targeted outcomes of NASA's Space Launch Initiative. One way to achieve this objective is through the replacement of metallic cryogenic fuel-tanks with polymer matrix composite (PMC) tanks for reusable launch vehicles (RLVs) as well as expendable launch vehicles (ELVs). For this purpose, however, the polymer matrix composite (PMC) tanks should be able to withstand flight loads and temperatures ranging from -250°C to 120°C without loss of cryogenic fuel due to permeation caused by the evolution of matrix cracks and delaminations. The micro-cracks result mainly due to the mismatch in the Poisson's ratio and/or coefficient of thermal expansion between adjacent plies of different orientation. These transverse matrix cracks in conjunction with inter-ply delaminations originating from the tips of these cracks result in an intersecting network of passages that could allow fuel to permeate. As depicted by the schematic in Fig. 1, the crack opening displacements associated with the delaminated transverse matrix cracks, when

subjected to thermal and/or mechanical loading, form a path through the entire thickness of the cross-ply laminate, thereby allowing cryogenic fuel to permeate. In order to study the permeation problem it is necessary to find an analytical solution for *delaminated crack opening displacement* (DCOD) as it will be shown later that the main factors influencing the permeability of cryogenic fuel are the DCOD and the crack density in each ply. Once the solutions for DCOD have been obtained, a mathematical model for predicting permeability of symmetric cross-ply graphite-epoxy laminates can be established.

II. Literature Review

Because of the potentially mission-critical implications of the permeation problem, many researchers have studied the permeation or leakage of cryogenic fuel through composite laminates through experiments [1-4]. McManus *et al* [1] observed that permeability is strongly influenced by loading conditions, crack density and ply orientation. Kumazawa *et al* [2] developed leak analysis based on the opening displacements of matrix cracks and observed that enlargement of crack opening displacement (COD) due to mechanical and thermal loads can cause increase in leak rate. Rivers *et al* [3] developed a method for measuring leakage through a geometrically complex structure at cryogenic temperature and under mechanical load and measured hydrogen leakage through complex X-33 liquid hydrogen tank structure sections. Yokozeki *et al* [4] experimentally investigated the leakage characteristics through micro-cracked laminates under cryogenic conditions (LN₂ temperature) and room temperature (RT) and found that leakage levels differ only slightly between two temperatures in spite of temperature-dependent molecular mobility.

Abdi *et al* [5] used the finite element method to predict the permeability as a function of strain, critical damage events and the contributing failure mechanisms associated with permeation. As presented in Fig. 1, the overlap area between cracks of two adjacent layers governs the permeation. Varna *et al* [6] predicted average COD based on shear-lag model and variational approach and found that the stiffness reduction in the uncracked layer influences the COD of the

Figure 1: Permeation path at overlap of two transverse crack with delaminations

interior layer. Roy and Benjamin [7] developed a simple expression for calculating the COD based on shear lag analysis. A limitation of shear lag analysis is that the constraining layers are assumed as a homogenous medium without taking into account the stacking sequence effects. Also, it can be seen from Fig. 1 that the increase in crack opening displacement due to delamination plays an important role in determining the amount of permeation of cryogenic fuel, which is not included in a standard shear lag model. Noh and Whitcomb [8] developed a simple expression for calculating the crack opening volume (COV) based on

changes in the effective moduli of a cracked ply and studied the effect of various parameters such as adjacent ply orientation, material properties of adjacent plies, initial properties of the cracked ply and cracks in adjacent ply on COV. More recently, Noh and Whitcomb [9] used 3D FEA to examine the effect of various parameters on the delamination growth and the opening near the intersection of transverse matrix cracks (TMC) and delamination and calculated the opening at the intersection of TMC's and delamination for cross-ply and angle ply laminates. They observed that the crack opening could be predicted using two-dimensional models when crack-tip delaminations are fully developed, and that interaction effects on COD due to matrix cracks in adjacent plies can be ignored. Gates *et al* [10] studied the effect of cryogenic

temperature on materials properties of IM7/PETI-5 and found that temperature, loading mode, and aging time can all have significant influence on residual strength and stiffness of the laminate, and this influence is a strong function of laminate stacking sequence. They also, observed that certain material properties, such as laminate moduli, are not only nonlinear but they may also be non-monotonic functions of temperature

Therefore it is necessary to develop a mathematical model to find the opening displacement associated with matrix cracks in the presence of delaminations. Using the analytical solution for matrix crack opening displacement associated with delaminations, an expression for permeability will be derived and verified using experimental data.

III. Problem Overview

As described in the previous section, in order to develop a mathematical model for prediction of permeability in graphite-epoxy laminates it is necessary to first predict the crack opening displacement in every layer that forms a path through the entire thickness of the laminate as shown in Fig. 1. Once the crack opening displacement is known for given set of thermal and/or mechanical loads, the permeability can be predicted by modifying the micro-crack model suggested by Kumazawa [2].

In this study, an analytical methodology based on first-order shear laminate theory [11] is applied to predict opening displacement associated with delaminations in a $[0/90_n]_s$ cross-ply laminate system in the graphite-epoxy laminate (IM7/PETI-5) subject to thermal and mechanical loading conditions. Although it is feasible to include damage evolution in this model, delamination length and crack density are specified as input in the interest of simplicity. The models (Five-layer and Three-layer) presented in this study are based on the work originally presented by Zhang *et al* [12]. The five-layer model is used to predict DCOD in the 90° layer whereas the three-layer model is used to predict the DCOD in 0° layer.

Figure 2: Delamination Analysis Solved as two different cases

The DCOD obtained using both five-layer and three-layer model is verified using a two-dimensional finite element analysis. A mathematical model to predict permeability in graphite-epoxy laminate system is developed using Darcy's law for isothermal, viscous flow of gases through porous media. The results obtained from both five-layer and three-layer model are used as input to the permeability model.

IV. Introduction to Delaminated Crack Opening Displacement

In this section, an analytical solution for delaminated crack opening displacement (DCOD) is derived based on first-order shear laminate theory for a cross-ply laminate configuration. If a cross-ply laminate, as shown in Fig. 2, is under mechanical and or thermal loading, matrix cracking in the transverse plies (90°) is the first damage mode observed and is enhanced by an increasing applied load. Due to high local stresses at the crack tips, through-width uniform local delamination initiates from the transverse ply crack tips. Similar damage modes are seen in 0°

layers when the loading is bi-axial in nature. As depicted in Fig. 2, matrix cracking associated with delaminations in adjacent plies creates delaminated crack opening displacement (DCOD), throughout the thickness of the laminate. This allows the cryogenic fuel to permeate. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a mathematical solution to find DCOD in both 0° and 90° layers so that the results can be used in predicting the permeability of the cross-ply laminates subjected to thermal and mechanical loading. Matrix crack along with delamination in 90° layer is considered as Case 1 problem (see Fig. 3) and solved using the five-layer model. In the interest of space the Three Layer Model (TLM; Case 2) is not discussed.

A. Five Layer Model Laminate Analysis (Case 1)

In this section, an expression for Delaminated Crack Opening Displacement (DCOD) derived based on a two-dimensional first-order shear laminate theory [12] is applied to the five-layer model (FLM) laminate of ply orientation $[\theta_1/\theta_2/90_n]_s$ shown in Fig.3. Transverse matrix cracks are assumed to exist in the 90° plies with uniform crack spacing of $2S$. Local delaminations of length $2L$ are assumed to initiate and grow in a symmetric manner from tips of each transverse matrix crack and span the entire width of the laminate. Invoking symmetry of geometry and loading, only one quarter of the five-layer laminate is modeled as shown in Fig. 4, corresponding to Case 1 as discussed earlier. The modeled portion of laminate length S is divided into six sublaminates with three sublaminates (1,2,3) in the undamaged portion and three sublaminates (4,5,6) in the delaminated portion as shown numbered in Fig. 4. Plain strain condition is assumed in the width direction (x -direction) of the model. Three local coordinates, one for each sublaminates, are used for the model as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 3: Five-layer model for the cracked and delaminated laminate (case 1)

Assuming that the displacements in y and z directions within each sublaminates can be given by,

$$v(y, z) = V(y) + z\beta(y) \quad (1)$$

$$w = W(y) \quad (2)$$

where, $V(y)$ is the y displacement of mid-surface of the sublaminates, $\beta(y)$ is the slope of the sublaminates mid-surface in y direction, $W(y)$ is the z displacement of mid-surface of the sublaminates. Combining the strain-displacement relations [12] with Eqns. (1, 2) and the in-plane stress-strain relationships of a lamina, the force-displacement relationships of a sublaminates are,

$$N_M = A_{22}V_{,y} + B_{22}\beta_{,y} - \bar{Q}_{22}h \int_{T_{ref}}^{T_f} \alpha_y dT \quad (3)$$

$$M_M = B_{22}V_{,y} + D_{22}\beta_{,y} - \bar{Q}_{22}h \bar{z} \int_{T_{ref}}^{T_f} \alpha_y dT \quad (4)$$

$$Q = A_{44}(\beta + W_{,y}) \quad (5)$$

Figure 4: One quarter of the repeating interval of the five layer model laminate (case 1)

where, A_{22} , B_{22} , D_{22} and A_{44} are components of the A , B and D stiffness matrices from classical

lamination theory; h is the thickness of the lamina; \bar{z} is centroidal distance of the lamina from laminate midplane; α_y is the coefficient of thermal expansion in y -direction and is given by the nonlinear function $C_0+C_1T_f+C_2T_f^2$. In the above equations, non-linear material properties with respect to temperature T_f are used in calculating the thermal forces and moments. The components of A , B , D and \bar{Q} matrix are assumed to be nonlinear functions of temperature T_f . It should be noted that for a two-dimensional orthotropic model the other stiffness components of the anisotropic sublaminates do not appear in the constitutive equations due to the assumption of plane strain with respect to the width of the specimen. By following the procedure given by Zhang *et al* [12] the solutions for displacement in y direction of sublaminates 4 and 5 are derived as,

$$v^{(4)}(y, z) = V^{(4)}(y) + z^{(3)}\beta^{(4)}(y) \quad (6)$$

$$v^{(5)}(y, z) = V^{(5)}(y) + z^{(2)}\beta^{(5)}(y) \quad (7)$$

$$V^{(4)} = \psi_3 y + \psi_4 \quad (8)$$

$$V^{(5)} = -k_1(\theta_1 e^{\omega y} + \theta_2 e^{-\omega y}) + \theta_3 y + \theta_7 \quad (9)$$

$$\beta^{(4)} = \psi_1 \quad (10)$$

$$\beta^{(5)} = \theta_1 e^{\omega y} q + \theta_2 e^{-\omega y} q + \theta_3 y + \theta_4 \quad (11)$$

For obtaining laminate constants k_i , θ_i , ψ_i , and ω for the case of thermal and mechanical loading for the three-layer model, boundary conditions are applied to each sublaminate. In the interest of space a detailed derivation for the five-layer model is not presented in this paper, but is similar to the three-layer model [12].

From Eqns. (8)-(11), the delaminated crack opening displacement (DCOD) calculated at the interface of sublaminates 4 and 5 at $y=S$ for a given delamination length L and crack density $1/2S$ is given by,

$$DCOD = v^{(4)}\left(S, \frac{h^{(3)}}{2}\right) - v^{(5)}\left(S, \frac{-h^{(2)}}{2}\right) \quad (12)$$

Using Eqn. (12), DCOD for a given delamination length, crack density and symmetric loading (mechanical and/or thermal) condition can be obtained for the Case 1 laminate configuration.

B. Laminate with Arbitrary Ply Orientation

The FLM and TLM models can be enhanced to determine the delaminated crack opening displacement (DCOD) in the intermediate plies of a symmetric laminate with *arbitrarily oriented* plies. The model is based on first order shear deformation theory. The load conditions considered here are mechanical uniaxial tensile loading and thermal loading. Each layer is individually analyzed for crack assuming that the remaining layers are uncracked. It is assumed that plies with fibers perpendicular to load direction, i.e. 90° layer, are more susceptible to transverse matrix cracking. As the transverse matrix cracks are studied in this model, layers with ply orientations other than 90° are analyzed by resolving the applied global forces into components parallel and perpendicular to the fiber direction. This is done considering the rotation of coordinate system accordingly to view those layers as having orientation of 90° . Appropriate rotational transformations in loads and properties are applied to full RVE for analysis of the particular layer under consideration.

We define θ_R as the angle through which the cracked ply has to be rotated relative to the global x-y reference in order to view it as a layer of 90° degree orientation, i.e., for the local 1-direction of the cracked ply to be perpendicular to the global y-direction for FLM (global x-direction for TLM). Equations (13) & (14) below describe the force resolution. The primed variables in the equations reflect the rotated components while the unprimed variable refers to the global components of forces.

$$N'_x = N_x \cos \theta_R + N_y \sin \theta_R \quad (13)$$

$$N'_y = N_y \cos \theta_R - N_x \sin \theta_R \quad (14)$$

where,

$$N_x = N_x (\text{Mechanical}) + N_x (\text{Thermal}) \quad (15a)$$

$$N_y = N_y (\text{Mechanical}) + N_y (\text{Thermal}) \quad (15b)$$

Eqns. (13-15) were implemented in the FLM and TLM analyses, and a quasi-isotropic laminate configuration, $[45/0/-45/90]_s$, was analyzed using the enhanced model to predict DCOD in each ply (see results section).

V. Permeability Modeling

Using Darcy's law the expression for permeability B_o can be obtained as,

$$B_o = C \cdot \left[\sum_{K=1}^N \left(\frac{\text{Sin} \hat{\theta}}{h_K \cdot N_K \cdot N_{K+1} \cdot \Delta_K \cdot \Delta_{K+1}} \right) \right]^{-1} \quad (16)$$

Where,

$$C = \frac{\hat{C}RT\eta}{MP_{AVG}} \quad (17)$$

Δ_K is Delaminated crack opening displacement in K^{th} ply, Δ_{K+1} is Delaminated crack opening displacement in $K+1^{\text{th}}$ ply, d_K width of interlaminar delamination associated with the crack in K^{th} ply, d_{K+1} width of interlaminar delamination associated with the crack in $K+1^{\text{th}}$ ply. $\hat{\theta}$ is angle between fiber directions in K^{th} and $(K+1)^{\text{th}}$ ply, η is the viscosity of the flowing gas, P_{AVG} is the average of pressures across the boundary, M is the molecular weight of the gas, R is the universal gas constant, T is the temperature, \hat{C} is a material constant that needs to be characterized from experiment.

From Eq. (17), it is evident that permeability is a function of crack densities, delaminated crack opening displacements and delamination width, and can be determined once the average crack densities and delaminated crack opening displacements are characterized for a laminate. A detailed procedure for permeability characterization experiment is presented by McManus [1] and is not separately discussed here.

VI. Finite Element Model

Figure 5: 2D-Finite element model of a laminate with delaminated cracks

A two-dimensional finite element model as shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 was constructed to compute Delaminated Crack Opening Displacement (DCOD) occurring in laminates subjected to thermal or mechanical loads for Case 1 configuration. Finite element (FE) analyses were performed using the commercial finite element software, IDEAS. Due to symmetry of geometry and loading, only one half of the specimen was modeled as shown in Fig. 5. Because of

plane strain assumption in the XY-plane, a two-dimensional mesh consisting of 8-noded plane strain elements was used instead of a full 3-D finite element analysis.

First, the FE analysis was performed for $[0/90_2]_S$ laminate for Case 1 configuration as shown in Fig. 5 and the DCOD along the crack face was obtained from the computed displacement of the nodes at the 0/90 interface. The finite element analyses were performed for both thermal and mechanical loading conditions with the delamination length varying from 0.125 cm to 0.50 cm. The DCOD values predicted by FE analysis were compared with results obtained from the five-layer model (Case 1) and results were found to be in agreement in both cases as presented in next section.

VII. Comparison of Delaminated Crack opening Displacement with FEA

Table 1: Material Properties of IM7/PETI-5, Gates et al [10]

E_{11}	E_{22}	E_{33}	G_{12}	G_{13}	G_{23}	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}	α_1	α_2
(GPa)			(GPa)						$(\times 10^{-6} \text{ } \epsilon/^{\circ}\text{C})$	
166.8	8.82	8.82	5.03	5.03	3.30	0.3	0.3	0.34	-1.30	19.44

A $[0/90_2]_S$ cross-ply, IM7/PETI-5 graphite/epoxy laminate system is considered here. The basic material properties of an IM7/PETI-5 composite lamina are given in Table 1. The material property coefficients are given in Table 2. These coefficients are used in the equation of the form, Property (T_f) = $C_0 + C_1 T_f + C_2 T_f^2$ (T_f in $^{\circ}\text{C}$) for calculating the non-linear material properties with respect to temperature T_f .

Table 2: Material property coefficients of IM7/PETI-5, Gates et al [10]

Property	C_0	C_1	C_2
E_{11} (GPa)	1.64×10^{11}	7.74×10^7	0.12×10^6
E_{22}, E_{33} (GPa)	8.29×10^9	2.00×10^7	8.37×10^4
G_{12}, G_{13} (GPa)	5.08×10^9	-2.62×10^6	8.54×10^3
G_{23} (GPa)	3.34×10^9	-1.73×10^6	5.40×10^3
ν_{12}, ν_{13}	0.30	-	-
ν_{23}	0.34	-	-
α_1 ($\epsilon/^{\circ}\text{C}$)	-1.05×10^{-6}	-8.92×10^{-9}	-5.68×10^{-11}
α_2 ($\epsilon/^{\circ}\text{C}$)	1.98×10^{-5}	-1.69×10^{-8}	-8.30×10^{-11}

Firstly, the DCOD found using the five-layer model for Case 1 is compared with the finite element analysis for both mechanical and thermal loading conditions, respectively. The uniaxial mechanical load applied is a tensile force of $N=4500\text{N}$ applied in the y-direction (refer to Fig. 4). For all the analyses in this section, the transverse ply crack half-spacing S was chosen to be 1.25 cm, which corresponds to a crack density of 0.4 cm^{-1} . In Fig. 6, the DCOD for a delamination at 0/90 interface in the $[0/90_2]_S$ laminate calculated by five layer model (FLM; Case 1) and finite element model (FEA) are plotted versus the delamination length which is varied from 0.125 cm to 0.50 cm. Good agreement between FEA and the FLM model is observed.

Figure 6: DCOD vs. Delamination Length in $[0/90_2]_S$ for mechanical loading (Case 1)

Figure 7: DCOD vs. Delamination Length in $[0/90_2]_S$ for Thermal Loading (Case 1)

Fig. 7 shows a similar comparison for the case of pure thermal loading of $\Delta T = -278^\circ\text{C}$. The non-linear variation of material properties with respect to temperature T_f is used for calculating the DCOD and the results for both linear (FLM-L) and non-linear (FLM-NL) properties are shown in Fig. 7. It can be observed that the effect of nonlinear material behavior on DCOD with respect to temperature is not very significant. So it is assumed that non linear properties of laminate material do not change significantly with temperature, as data is not available at various temperatures. Good agreement between the five-layer model and 2D finite element model suggests that the five-layer model can accurately predict the DCOD for a given delamination length and mechanical/thermal loading conditions for Case 1. Interestingly, in all of the above cases a linear variation of DCOD with increasing delamination length is observed.

VIII. Comparison of DCOD for Laminates with Arbitrary Ply Orientations

Figure 8: Crack Profile Comparison TLM – FEA. [45/0/-45/90]s laminate with crack in 45° layer (TLM)
For $\Delta T = -495^\circ\text{F}$, $L=0.01''$, $S=0.25''$

Figure 9: Crack Profile Comparison FLM – FEA. [45/0/-45/90]s laminate with crack in 0° layer (FLM)
For $\Delta T = -495^\circ\text{F}$, $L=0.01''$, $S=0.25''$

Figures 8 through 11 show the through-thickness DCOD predicted by the enhanced FLM-TLM code for a [45/0/-45/90]s laminate for each layer, and compared with 3-D Finite Element Analysis (FEA) for the case of thermal loading only. The vertical orange line in the figures indicates initial position of the crack prior to loading. Predicted results for DCOD at the top and bottom of each lamina are summarized in Table 3, together with FEA predictions, and the error relative to FEA predictions are also tabulated. It can be seen from the figures and the Table that the enhanced FLM-TLM code predictions are generally in good agreement with FEA results, except for the 45° ply. A crack density of 2 cracks/inch and a delamination length of $L= 0.01$ inch was assumed for the analyses. It should be noted that the linear through-thickness variation of DCOD predicted by the enhanced FLM-TLM analysis is due to the fact that the model uses a first-order shear deformable theory. Use of a higher-order theory would mitigate this discrepancy; however our attempts to employ a second-order shear-deformation theory have resulted in equations that are not amenable to closed form solutions.

Figure 10: Crack Profile Comparison FLM – FEA. [45/0/-45/90]_s laminate with crack in -45° layer (FLM)
 For $\Delta T = -495^\circ\text{F}$, $L=0.01''$, $S=0.25$

Figure 11: Crack Profile Comparison FLM – FEA. [45/0/-45/90]_s laminate with crack in 90° layer (FLM)
 For $\Delta T = -495^\circ\text{F}$, $L=0.01''$, $S=0.25''$

For all of the above analyses good agreement between analytical models and finite element analysis was observed. However, it should be noted that this study was performed based on the assumption that the laminate consists of pre-existing cracks with symmetric delaminations without considering progressive crack growth with load increase. Also, it was assumed that there is no interaction between cracks in adjacent layers, thereby enabling superposition of results obtained from both five-layer and three layer model to calculate permeability.

Table 3: DCOD Predictions: Enhanced FLM/TLM – 3D FEA ([45/0/-45/90]_s laminate)

[45/0/-45/90] _s		S	L		
				0.25 inch	
				0.01 inch	
ΔT		-495 °F			
Layer		FLM DCOD Inch	3D FEA DCOD Inch	% Error	
45°	Top	2.96x10 ⁻⁴	2.88x10 ⁻⁴	2.694	TLM
45°	Bottom	6.10x10 ⁻⁵	8.60x10 ⁻⁵	29	TLM
0°	Top	1.27x10 ⁻⁴	1.24x10 ⁻⁴	2.42	FLM
0°	Bottom	1.35x10 ⁻⁴	1.26x10 ⁻⁴	7.14	FLM
-45°	Top	2.13x10 ⁻⁴	2.06x10 ⁻⁴	3.39	FLM
-45°	Bottom	2.25x10 ⁻⁴	2.22x10 ⁻⁴	1.35	FLM
90°	Top	9.26x10 ⁻⁵	8.34x10 ⁻⁵	10.95	FLM
90°	Bottom	1.59x10 ⁻⁴	1.50x10 ⁻⁴	6.48	FLM

A. Modeling Interaction between matrix cracks using 3-D FEA

Figure 12: Interaction between matrix cracks using 2D and 3D configurations

In order to study the effects of interaction between transverse matrix cracks in 0° and 90° layers, a sensitivity analysis was performed using 3-D FEA and comparing the results with the five-layer model and with 2-D FEA. Thermal loading $\Delta T = -132^\circ\text{C}$ was applied to the cross-ply laminate $[0/90_2]_s$, having delamination length $L = 0.50\text{ cm}$. Using 3-D FEA, delaminated crack opening (DCOD) for two distinct cases were obtained. First, a 3-D model with cracks in 90° was analyzed for DCOD in 90° layer without modeling cracks in the 0° layer. Second, 3-D model with delaminated cracks in both 0° and 90° layers was analyzed and DCOD in 90° layer was obtained. It can be seen from Fig. 12 that the DCOD in both cases were almost identical implying that the cracks in 0° layer do not have a

significant effect on the opening of cracks in the 90° layer. This implies that the interaction between intersecting cracks in adjacent layers is negligible and that DCOD can be determined individually for each layer and then superposed to find permeability using Eqn. (16). Therefore, superposition of results obtained from Case 1 and Case 2 is justified in this case.

Results from 2-D FEA and five-layer model for delaminated crack opening in 90° layer are also shown in Fig. 12 for comparison. It can be seen that the results between these two analyses are same and also it can be seen that the 2-D models predicts slightly higher delaminated crack opening than 3-D FEA, and therefore can be expected to provide slightly conservative prediction of permeation.

B. Permeability modeling results

The DCOD values obtained using both five-layer and three layer model can be superposed to predict the permeability values for $[0/90_2]_s$ laminate for a given crack density and loading as described in section 3. In this section, normalized laminate permeability (B_o/C), obtained from Eqn. (16), is predicted. The material constant \hat{C} can be found using the experimental characterization of permeability as discussed in section 3.

In Fig. 13, B_o/C is plotted versus crack density in middle ply group (90° layer) for different delamination lengths for a thermal loading of $\Delta T = -278^\circ\text{C}$. The crack density in 0° layer is assumed to be 0.4 cm^{-1} . The delamination length in the 0° layer is assumed to be same as that of the 90° layer. From Fig. 13, it can be observed that normalized permeability approaches a plateau with increasing crack density. This is because as crack density increases, the peak tensile stress in the uncracked ligament starts to decrease, thereby reducing the delaminated crack opening displacement.

In order to study the behavior of permeability as a function of thermal loading (ΔT), normalized permeability is plotted against thermal loading in Fig. 14. It can be seen from the graph that

Figure 13: Normalized permeability (B_o/C) vs. Cracks per cm in middle ply group in $[0/90_2]_s$ for Thermal Loading.

Figure 14: Normalized permeability (B_o/C) vs. thermal Loading in $[0/90_2]_s$ laminate

Figure 15: Normalized permeability (B_o/C) vs. Mechanical Loading in $[0/90_2]_s$ laminate

Figure 16: Normalized permeability (B_o/C) vs. delamination length for different crack densities for thermal loading in $[0/90_2]_s$

permeability increases almost parabolically, as

increased thermal loading causes the transverse matrix cracks to open up further. Similar behavior is predicted for mechanical loading as well. Figure 15 shows the behavior of permeability as a function of mechanical loading N_y (and N_x). For both analyses, the crack half-spacing S was chosen to be 1.25 cm, which corresponds to a crack density of 0.4 cm^{-1} and delamination length $L=0.125\text{cm}$ for both 90° (Case 1) and 0° (Case 2) layers. Figure 16 shows the behavior of permeability as a function of delamination length in middle ply group (90° layer) for different crack densities & Thermal loading $\Delta T = -278^\circ\text{C}$. The crack density in the 0° layer is assumed to be 0.4cm^{-1} and delamination length $L= 0.125\text{cm}$. It can be seen from the graph that as delamination length increases normalized permeability approaches a plateau with increasing delamination length. This is because the peak tensile stress in the uncracked ligament starts to decrease with increasing delamination length, thereby reducing the delaminated crack opening displacement.

IX. Conclusion

In this study, an expression for predicting opening displacement due to delamination was derived based on first-order shear laminate theory applied to five-layer and three-layer models. Using this expression, the DCOD can be calculated for a cross-ply laminate with a given delamination length, crack density and loading conditions. The DCOD predictions for cross-ply laminate showed excellent agreement with finite element analysis results. Even though the present version of the five-layer model is limited to orthotropic sublaminates only, it can be modified to include anisotropic sublaminate behavior, which can then be used to study the effects of stacking sequence and adjacent ply orientation on DCOD. In this study, an expression for predicting permeability of graphite-epoxy laminate system was derived based on Darcy's law for isothermal, viscous flow of gases through porous media and micro-crack model. The DCOD values predicted from both five-layer and three-layer models are used as input to the permeability modeling equation. Using this equation, the permeability can be calculated for an orthotropic laminate lay-up for a given delamination length, crack density and loading conditions. The model was enhanced to include laminates of arbitrary orientation, and the enhanced model was verified by comparison with 3-D FEA. The predicted permeability can be verified using experiments and this will be the future work involved in this study. These observations were made for IM7/PETI-5 graphite epoxy laminate system and these conclusions may not be transferable to other type of laminates.

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